

ATTRACTING FOREIGN INVESTMENTS THROUGH CORPORATE SECURITIES

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Abstract. In this article, the opinions and approaches of various researchers on the capital market, corporate securities and foreign investments are studied in the study of the possibilities of attracting foreign investments through corporate securities. The current state of attracting foreign investments through corporate securities, the participation of foreign investors in the stock market,] and foreign investments in the bond market have been analyzed. On the basis of the performed analysis, appropriate conclusions and proposals are formed.

Keywords: securities, corporate securities, stock, corporate bond, capital market, investment, foreign investment, investment attractiveness.

In every country, the capital market plays an important role in attracting foreign investments. It should be noted that securities issued by corporate structures on the stock market are among the financial instruments that investors are most interested in. If we look at the international experience, while dozens of types of shares and corporate bonds are widely used, a number of problems remain in the traditional corporate securities practices in the capital market of our country. In addition, there is a need to attract foreign investments in developing countries, and in this process, it is necessary to effectively use the opportunities of corporate securities. Therefore, it is important to study the possibilities of attracting foreign investments through corporate securities.

A lot of research is being done on increasing the possibilities of attracting

foreign investments through corporate securities. According to A. Andries, "today, the capital market is one of the main components of any modern economy. The capital market is a very dynamic and innovative structure that constantly adapts to the economic environment and, at the same time, is an influential factor in it, creating opportunities and equally threatening for all categories of participants" [1]. It is necessary to take into account its features in the development of the capital market.

M. Naeem et al. "the study of stock market returns is important for both researchers and practitioners. In particular, the empirical analysis of returns on securities is relevant for a number of reasons, including the identification and understanding of the main sources of risk and return in financial markets, risk diversification, etc. [2] kid Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to risks in the practice of corporate securities.

The team of authors led by Z.Yin concluded that "the liberalization of the stock market attracts more foreign investors, and enterprises tend to implement effective corporate governance to increase market competitiveness and increase their motivation to disclose internal information. Increasing market competition leads to competition between companies to increase the quality and transparency of information disclosure in order to reduce information asymmetry, meet market demand and prevent negative reactions" [3]. Today, information is gaining importance in the capital market as well as in other areas. Therefore, it is necessary to positively solve the issues of information asymmetry and information disclosure.

J. Kurbanov and others highlighted the importance of public placement practices in attracting local and foreign investments in the capital market. "Through the initial public offering of shares (IPO), it is possible to attract a large amount of capital (funds), achieve an increase in the price of shares, increase investment attractiveness, and build one's international image. It is necessary to

recognize the high importance of institutional investors selected as financial advisers and underwriters" [6]. In this process, not only the possibility of attracting a large amount of capital increases, but also the intermediary services in the capital market are developed.

In the effective organization of corporate securities operations, it is necessary to use various forms of public placement of shares. According to A. Karimov, "off-exchange placement of shares - DPO (Direct Public Offering) is usually a direct offer of company securities to an investor bypassing the stock market, while new shareholding public placement of shares on the stock exchange - IPO (Initial Public Offering), secondary placement process - Follow-on, public placement of the company's securities (shares, bonds, depository receipts) - RRO (Primaries Public Offering), major shareholder's the process of public placement of shares is called SPO (Secondary Public Offering), the closed placement of shares for certain categories of investors is called PO (Private placement or Private Offering), the process of public placement of shares at the same time when shareholders agree is called RVO (Piggyback Offering)" [7]. The use of these forms of public placement of shares in the national practice allows attracting enterprises of different types of ownership to the capital market.

The team of authors led by N. Shavkatov studied the importance of infrastructure bonds in the capital market, their characteristics, and taxation of income from these securities. In particular, it is necessary to provide tax benefits from the income received by investing in infrastructure bonds. In this case, by not applying the tax rate charged as interest income to the income received from the financing of infrastructure bonds, we will be able to increase the volume of attracting investors to financing" [8]. Therefore, it is necessary to create favorable taxation mechanisms for foreign investors in order to start trading of various financial instruments in the capital market and thereby expand the attraction of foreign capital.

Taking into account the opinions of these scientists and researchers, it can be noted that in expanding the practice of attracting foreign capital through corporate securities, attention should be paid to such things as ensuring the diversity of financial instruments, increasing their profitability, and forming a favorable taxation system for foreign investors. should be focused.

Increasing trade in capital market instruments, in particular, corporate securities, is important for economic development and attracting foreign investments to the economy. In the practice of developing countries, including Uzbekistan, foreign capital plays an important role in economic development. Today, we will analyze below the current situation of attracting foreign investments through corporate securities in the national capital market at a certain level.

Figure2. Indicators of corporate bonds belonging to foreign investors in the stock market[9]

Figure 2 shows the analysis of corporate bonds belonging to foreign

investors in the capital market, and as of October 1, 2023, the total volume of corporate bonds is 1001.8 billion. is soum. 25.4 billion from the total volume of corporate bonds. Soum corporate bonds or 3 percent of the total volume of corporate bonds are owned by foreign investors.

Figure 4. Analysis of shares issued by industry (1.10.2023) [10]

If we analyze the share issuers in the current state of the national capital market by sectors, 47% of the issued shares belong to the industrial sector, and 37% were issued by companies belonging to the financial sector. Companies in the service sector issued 11 percent of the total shares, while the agricultural sector recorded the lowest figure with 5 percent.

Based on the study of the possibilities of attracting foreign investments through corporate securities, the following conclusions were formed:

corporate securities are the main financial instruments in the capital market. Therefore, in each developing country, including Uzbekistan, it is necessary to develop special strategies for the expansion of the practice of these financial instruments in the development of the capital market. .

it is necessary to develop mechanisms of state regulation and self-regulation by regulatory bodies to increase trading of corporate securities on the capital market;

In order to increase the sale of traditional corporate securities in the capital market, it is necessary to effectively organize the dividend policy in enterprises, improve the financial indicators of enterprises and increase their investment attractiveness.

in attracting foreign investments through corporate securities, it is desirable to strengthen the integration of the local stock exchange with foreign stock exchanges and to pay attention to the development of the capital market infrastructure.

List of used literature

1. Alin Marius Andrieş. THE IMPORTANCE OF CAPITAL MARKET IN ECONOMY. // CES Working Papers, I, (2), 2009

2. Muhammad Abubakr Naeem, Ioannis Chatziantoniou, David Gabauer, Sitara Karim. Measuring the G20 stock market return transmission mechanism: Evidence from the R2 connectedness approach. // International Review of Financial Analysis, Volume 91, January 2024.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1057521923005021>

3. Zhichao Yin, Xinqi Li, Dengkui Si, Xiaolin Li. China stock market liberalization and company ESG performance: The mediating effect of investor attention. // Economic Analysis and Policy, Volume 80, December 2023, Pages 1396-1414.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0313592623002692>

4. Hongpan Zhang, Jiayue Zhao. Stock market liberalization and financial reporting quality. // China Journal of Accounting Research, Available online 26 September 2023.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1755309123000382>

5. Elmirzayev S., Omonov S. DIVIDEND POLICY ANALYSIS IN DEVELOPED COUNTRIES AND DIVIDEND ARISTOCRATS //International Finance and Accounting. – 2020. – T. 2020. – №. 2. – C. 22.

6. Jorabekovich Q. J. i dr. Analysis of international IPO practices: organizational features and participation of institutional investors // Economics and finance (Uzbekistan). – 2021. – no. 1 (137). - S. 53-61.

7. A.I. Karimov The importance of public placement practices in attracting investors to the stock market, Finance magazine, 2023, issue 5

8. Shavkatov N., Rakhmedova M., Bozorov U. ISSUES OF ATTRACTING THE PRIVATE SECTOR IN PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP THROUGH INFRASTRUCTURE BONDS //International Finance and Accounting. – 2021. – T. 2021. – №. 1. – C. 23.

9. <https://depo.uzcsd.uz/api/Website/GetPdfById1569>-The depository is formed on the basis of information from the data center

10. <https://depo.uzcsd.uz/api/Website/GetPdfById1569>-The depository is formed on the basis of information from the data center